

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: BABALOLA****FIRST NAME: DAMILARE****PROGRAM CODE: DGG****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: QUIZ****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 6%

The author used the following software: (MSWord Microsoft 365 on Windows 11)

QUIZ FOR ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING (ACA-401D)

1. The following statements are true about academic writing except for one.
 - It provides answers to hypotheses.
 - It must be published after it is completed.**¹
 - It seeks to communicate ideas based on evidence.
 - It can include research findings, theses, or monographs.
2. All but one is not a rule of thumb when writing an academic paper.
 - Ensure to state clearly the thesis of the paper, ideally at the beginning of the paper.
 - Stay focused on your discussion points.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 4th ed (Bangui: Euclid University, 2001), 7.

- Ensure to support all assertions, views, and ideas raised with evidence.
- Keep writing as long as you have something to say without minding the length of your sentences.**²
3. Your success as a researcher depends on the following factors but one.
- Ability to craft your topic clearly.**³
- Ability to gather and analyse data.
- Ability to present your reasoning and claims as contributing to the body of knowledge in your research area.
- Ability to invite your readers to think critically about your evidence and claim.
4. In academic writing, a problem is
- Something that the researcher must avoid at all costs.
- Something sought out or invested by the researcher to investigate.**⁴
- An issue debated within the researcher's circle of friends and colleagues.
- A situation or event happening in the environment but not really of interest to the researcher.
5. Secondary sources are called the "*field literature*" because

² Ibid., 12-14.

³, Kate L Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. [Wayne C. Booth](#), [Gregory G. Colomb](#), [Joseph Bizup](#), [Joseph M. Williams](#), [William T. FitzGerald](#), 9th ed (Chicago: Chicago University Press, 2018), 19-23.

⁴ Ibid., 28-29.

- They help researchers to keep up with current research and find other points in their specific field to support their claims.⁵**
- They are open sources that anyone can access.
- They are neither easy nor hard to read.
- They don't really exist.
6. A beginner researcher can develop effective writing skills by
- Writing under pressure and chasing the deadline.
- Writing in marathon sessions.
- Writing the draft regularly and often, focusing on small goals and a reasonable quota of words to achieve.⁶**
- Read more and more when you don't feel like writing.
7. Citation is not required when
- Ideas, data, or methods can only be attributable to any source consulted.
- When ideas being expressed is your original idea.⁷**
- Quotes are made from exact words from a source.
- Ideas associated with a specific source are paraphrased or re-phrased.
8. One of the following must be avoided when crafting your dissertation title

⁵ Ibid., 36.

⁶ Ibid., 76.

⁷ Ibid., 139-140.

- A clear description of the research topic and/or problem and scope of the study.
- A general capture of the central thrust of your research.
- A reflection of the essence and purpose of your study.
- A trendy and elaborate literary language.** ⁸

9. As you reach the final stage of your dissertation, it is vital to

- Check that each element flows sequentially and logically.** ⁹
- Make provision to publish your unapproved paper.
- Confirm the date and time for your dissertation defence with your professor.
- Give your manuscript to a professional proofreader.

10. Four crucial concepts when employing a qualitative research method are

- Research problem, location of study, availability of resources, and a research group.
- Source citation, research questions, data availability, and funding for fieldwork.
- The research problem, purpose, questions, and data required for the study.** ¹⁰
- The interest of your supervisor, purpose, hypotheses, and research topic.

⁸ Linda D. Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 4th ed (Los Angeles: Sage Publication, 2019), 65-66.

⁹ Ibid., 710-711.

¹⁰ Ibid., 430-35; Phillips Adu, *Writing The Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study* (YouTube, 2016), 65:17 min., <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KRHvxY3N708>.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.